

IMPROVING ELECTRIC POWER AVAILABILITY IN POULTRY FARMS USING INTELLIGENT STANDALONE HYBRID RENEWABLE ENERGY SYSTEM

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Abstract: The decrease in the production capacity of some poultries and sudden death of the birds in these poultries are as a result of not having ideal power that will make some of these poultries to function efficiently. This was overcome by introducing improved electric power availability in the poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State for an increased output using intelligent standalone hybrid renewable energy system. This was done by characterizing the availability of electric power in poultry farm, establishing the causes of power unavailability in poultry farm in AMOLI community in Enugu State that triggered the low production capacity, determining available sources of renewable energy that will boost electric power availability in poultry farm at AMOLI community and subsequently improved its production capacity. The study designed a standalone rule-base that improves the availability of the electric power in poultry farm thereby enhancing its production capacity. A Simulink model used for improving the availability of electric power in poultry farm was designed. The percentage improvement of the availability of electric power and its production capacity in poultry farm at AMOLI community in Enugu State were validated and justified. The result obtained with the conventional electric power availability in poultry farm was 70KW that caused low production in the poultry. This was because conventional electric power could not meet the threshold of 72 through 75KW. On the other hand, when standalone was integrated in the system it becomes 73.78KW thereby improving the production capacity of the poultry and the number of chickens hatched in poultry farm at the community was 1000 with the conventional while when standalone was integrated in the system hatched chickens were 1054. With these results the percentage improvement in the production capacity of the poultry was 5.4%.

Keywords: Electric Power, Availability, Poultry Farm, Intelligent Standalone Fuzzy Inference System, Hybrid, Renewable Energy System.

I. INTRODUCTION

The cause of death of some of the poultry birds are as a result of poor power supplied in the farm to run the equipment used in these poultries (Inegei, 2010). The growth of any poultry farm lies on adequate power supply

to sustain the poultry thereby enhancing its production capacity (Nguyen, 2012). It is crystal clear that adequate water supply in the farm helps to boost the growth and healthy of the birds (Oviedo, 2009). This is attainable through instrumentation of innovative power equipments usable in agricultural sector which poultry is non exclusive, as well as deploying relevant mechanism towards increasing output. This is otherwise known as agro technology instrumentation (Okolotu *et al.*, 2018).

The term “poultry” covers a wide range of birds, from indigenous and commercial breeds of chickens to Muscovy ducks, turkeys, guinea fowl, geese, quail, pigeons, ostriches and pheasants (FAO, 2024; Okolotu *et al.*, 2024). In 2020, the global chicken population was over 33 billion birds, providing 93% of the world egg production; 90 percent of world poultry meat production, followed by turkey with 5 percent, ducks with 4 percent and geese and guinea fowl with 2 percent (Okolotu *et al.*, 2024).

II. MATERIALS

The major materials used in this research include: the study area (Amoli community village in Enugu State). Enugu is located in the southern part of Nigeria in West Africa.

Location of Enugu State in Map of Nigeria (Okolotu *et al.* 2017)

Other materials include: Solar panels, Battery Bank, Wind turbine, *etc.*

III. METHODOLOGY

The methods used in this study were the field work, analytical and simulation techniques for a typical poultry farm at Amoli community village. This was done by characterizing the availability of electric power in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State with a typical four houses. The equipment used per house and their power consumption per each equipment were stated in the table below;

Table 1: Total Starting vs Continuous Maximum Wattage Requirements for a Four-House Broiler Farm

Equipment (per house)	Running Watts	Cold - Start Watts
10, 1-hp fans	10,000	30,000
6, 3/4-hp feeder motors	2,010	20,100
2, 1-hp water pumps	2,000	6,000
50, 75-watt lights	3,750	3,750
Total demand per house	17,760	59,850
Four houses:	71,040	239,400
Water pump:	3,000	11,000
Four-house totals	74,040	250,400

The causes of power unavailability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State which triggered to its low production capacity were established and depicted at Table2.

Table 2: Causes of Power Unavailability in Poultry Farm

Metric or parameter	POULTRY FARM
POWER (KW)	70KW (Standard 72 - 75 KW)
Four-house totals Running Watts	73000W (Standard 74,040W to 75,000W)
Four-house totals Cold-Start Watts	24,800W (Std25,040W to 27,000W)
Quantity (CHICKENS)hatched	1000 CHICKENS

The established causes of power unavailability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State which triggered to its low production capacity as shown in table 2 has arisen as a result of power availability not meeting its standard threshold of 72KW through 75KW that is specified for four poultry houses in Amoli community.

Fig 1: Conventional Simulink Model for Electric Power Availability in Poultry Farm

To determine available sources of renewable energy that will boost electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community and subsequently improved its production capacity. The following calculations of power consumption per equipment were calculated below.

Solar panels

44 panels at 250watts each were used, and that’s makes the work to get

$$44 \times 250 = 11000\text{watts.} = 11\text{KW}$$

To find how many panels 75KW which was the peak of the threshold the poultry requires to function effectively.

11KW = 44 panels

$$75KW = \frac{44 * 75}{11}$$

300 panels of solar at 250 watts each are required to boost the poultry electric power availability.

The solar power required in the poultry becomes

$$300 \times 250 = 75000W = 75KW$$

The current rating of each 250watts was 10.59Amp.

$$\frac{250watts}{23.6} (23.6 \text{ is a constant value}) = 10.59$$

10.59 x 300 = 3177Amp. It was connected in series parallel to maintain the current. A total of 600 panels were used.

Battery Bank

44panels require 190 pieces of 2V, 200A

To find the number of 2V, 200A batteries required to run the 300panels for the poultry in Amoli.

44 panels = 190 pieces of batteries

$$300panels = \frac{190 * 300}{44} = 1296$$

1296 batteries were required to run 300 solar panels for the poultry in Amoli.

1296pieces of 2V, 200A connected in series = $\frac{2592V}{200A}$

It was then connected in parallel to give $\frac{2592V}{400A}$

Wind turbine

The capacity of wind turbine used was rated $\frac{75KW}{3177A}$

To design standalone rule-base that improves electric power availability in poultry farm at AMOLI community in Enugu State with improved production capacity a fuzzy inference system was designed. The system is shown in the figure 2 and 3 below. The system has three inputs of grid, wind energy, solar energy and an output that displayed the results.

Fig 2: Designed Standalone Fuzzy Inference System

Fig 3: Designed Standalone Rule Base

The comprehensive fully analysis of the standalone rule-base that improves electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State with improved production capacity was shown in Table 3 below;

Table 3: Comprehensive Developed Standalone Rule-Base

	Grid energy	Wind energy	Solar energy	Output
1	If grid energy is not within the standard of 72 to 75kw of the poultry farm improve	and wind energy is off when the grid is off switch on the wind energy automatically	and solar energy is off when the grid is off switch on the solar energy automatically	then result poor availability of power and poor chicken hatched in the poultry farm.
2	If grid energy is partially not within the standard of 72 to 75kw of the poultry farm improve	and wind energy is partially off when the grid is off switch on the wind energy automatically	and solar energy is partially off when the grid is off switch on the solar energy automatically	then result poor availability of power and poor chicken hatched in the poultry far
3	If grid energy is within the threshold of 72 and 75kw of poultry farm maintain	and wind energy is on when the grid energy is off maintained	and solar energy is on when the grid energy is off maintained	then result improved availability of power and many chicken hatched in the poultry farm

ASimulink model for standalone hybrid renewable energy stem

Continuous
powergui

Fig 4: Designed Simulink Model for Standalone Hybrid Renewable Energy Stem

Percentage improvement in electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State is expressed as;

$$\frac{S - C}{C} * 100\% = \frac{(73.78 - 70)KW}{70KW} * 100\% = 5.4\%$$

Where S = Standalone Hybrid Renewable Energy Power

C = Conventional Power

Therefore, the percentage improvement of electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State was 5.4%

The number of chickens hatched using Conventional power were 1000, whereas, the number of chickens hatched using Standalone hybrid renewable energy system were 1054

% improvement in number of chickens hatched when standalone hybrid renewable energy is incorporated in the system

$$\frac{\text{Standalone number of chickens hatched} - \text{Conventional number of chickens hatched}}{\text{Conventional number of chickens hatched}} * 100\%$$

% improvement in number of chickens hatched when standalone hybrid renewable energy is incorporated in the system is obtained as below;

$$= \frac{1054 - 1000}{1000} * 100\% = 5.4\%$$

The percentage improvement in number of chickens hatched when standalone hybrid renewable energy was incorporated in the system was also 5.4%

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESULT

The results obtained for the two scenarios were collected for seven (7) weeks and were tabulated in Table 4 below;

Table 4: Comparison of Conventional and Standalone Electric Power Availability in Poultry Farm at Amoli Community in Enugu State

Time(weeks)	Conventional electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State (KW)	Standalone electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State (KW)
1	70	73.78
2	70	73.78
3	70	73.78
4	70	73.78
5	70	73.78
6	70	73.78
7	70	73.78

Fig.5: Comparison of Conventional and Standalone Electric Power Availability in Poultry Farm at Amoli Community in Enugu State

The conventional electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu state was 70KW that cause low production in the poultry because it could not meet the threshold of 72 through 75KW. On the other hand, when Standalone was integrated in the system it becomes 73.78Kw thereby improving the production capacity of the poultry.

Table 5: Comparison of Conventional and Standalone Number of Chickens Hatched in Poultry Farm at Amoli Community in Enugu State

Time (weeks)	Conventional electric number of chickens hatched in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State (number)	Standalone number of chickens hatched in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State (number)
1	1000	1054
2	1000	1054
3	1000	1054
4	1000	1054
5	1000	1054
6	1000	1054
7	1000	1054

Fig. 6: Comparison of Conventional and Standalone number of chickens hatched in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State

The conventional number of chickens hatched in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu state is 1000 while when Standalone is integrated in the system it becomes 1054 hatched chickens. With these results the percentage improvement in the production capacity of the poultry was 5.4%.

V. CONCLUSION

The reduction in the production capacity of poultry has arisen as a result of not meeting the electrical power availability threshold of 72KW through 75KW. This equally led to the death of some of the chickens or broilers in the poultry thereby decreasing the financial status of the farm. This sudden death of the birds as a result of the electrical power availability not meeting the threshold of 72KW through 75KW that is specifically meant for the farm after visibility studies is subdued by introducing improved electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu state for an increased output using intelligent standalone hybrid renewable energy system. This is done in this manner, characterizing electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State, establishing the causes of power unavailability in poultry farm in Amoli community in Enugu State this triggered to its low production capacity, determining available sources of renewable energy that will boost electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community and subsequently improved its production capacity, designing standalone rule base that improves electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State with improved production capacity, designing a SIMULINK model for improving electric power availability in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu state for an increased output using intelligent standalone hybrid renewable energy system and validating and justifying percentage improvement in electric power availability and its production capacity

in poultry farm at Amoli community in Enugu State. The results obtained are the conventional electric power availability in poultryfarm at Amoli community in Enugu state is 70KW that cause low production in the poultry because it could not meet the thresh hood of 72 through 75KW. On the other hand, when Standalone is integrated in the system it becomes 73.78Kw thereby improving the production capacity of the poultry and the conventional number of chickens hatched in poultryfarm at Amoli community in Enugu state is 1000 while when Standalone is integrated in the system it becomes 1054 hatched chickens. With these results the percentage improvement in the production capacity of the poultry was 5.4%.

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